

A federated research infrastructure to boost the reuse of health data in population health research

Sustainability Fact Sheet

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Background

Nowadays, individual and potentially sensitive health data reuse is still scarce due to: data privacy and safety issues; difficulties in discovering data sources of value; complex access rules; uneven data quality; and, limited computational capacities. ^{1,2}

Previous European initiatives had shown the difficulties in the reuse and integration of multiple data sources containing different data types (including sensitive data) and curated in different premises. Mostly indicators-based projects, used anonymous data pooling after applying harmonisation procedures or provided safe remote access to de-identified data or implemented a partial federated approach to data analytics based on the distribution of code.^{3,4,5,6,7} In turn, similar federated approaches to PHIRI's had a limited scope in the type of research and domain of interest.⁸ These projects lacked a comprehensive and systematic approach to the interoperable reuse of sensitive data in a federated manner, a methodological approach addressing any type of data-driven research, or the proper implementation and deployment of technologies ensuring secure distribution and robust computing.

The COVID-19 pandemic has clearly demonstrated the urgent need for a cross-border and structured European mechanism to exchange, organize and access data, especially in the area of population health. PHIRI has implemented a federated multipurpose research infrastructure involving multiple data sources hosted in various European countries. The infrastructure has been deployed and tested in four research projects (namely, use cases) demonstrating how a broad variety of routine data can be linked and reused in a distributed way across Europe, aiming to address relevant policy questions on the indirect effects of the COVID19 pandemic on population health.

Main outcomes and results

- A standardized methodology for the governance of federated research that addresses the four layers of interoperability -legal, organisational, semantic and technological.
- PHIRI architecture that with a master-worker topology, has supported the deployment of four research projects.
- Software containers that act as secure processing environments where the analytical workflow is applied and results are shared.
- PHIRI App, a graphical user interface that facilitates the deployment of federated research
- Reproducible and interoperable digital objects, available in Zenodo and GitHub, for the reuse of other researchers in the field (see at <https://zenodo.org/record/6377134>)
- An App to automate the upload new dataset on existing research projects and produce new up-to-date comparable results (see at <https://www.healthinformationportal.eu/services/federated-demonstrators/phiri-use-case-b-demonstrator>)

Read more at [\[link to EJPH paper\]](#)

How the federated PHIRI approach could be enhanced

Enhancement of	Current gap	Need
Research initiation	No support to formally start a research study in the PHIRI research infrastructure	Create a platform for researchers to launch and scan research studies
Analysis scripts	Missing automatization to encapsulate the scripts and deploy the solutions	Create an open repository of existing containers of scripts, based on open APIs, that can be reused to create new codes and deploy them
Federated learning	No purely federated learning algorithms executed in the platform	Adapt or create existing federated learning algorithms to the population health context using open APIs and runtimes
Secure Transport	No protocol for secure data transport selected	Use secure transport layer, aligning with other data sharing initiatives in HealthData@EU and EOSC
Common Data Models	Working with bespoke data models may have in impact in scalability	Development and adoption of general-purpose data models
Computing Capacity	No sustainable computation capacity provision selected	Adopt EU supported computation capacity providers (e.g., EOSC)

Why the federated PHIRI approach shall be continued

The extensive and continuous reuse of sensitive health data (e.g., clinical data, electronic health or clinical records, administrative and claims data) will enhance the role of population health research on supporting policy decision making.

The implementation of the PHIRI federated methodology in the architecture has been proven effective in responding policy-relevant questions with health data that is potentially sensitive, while complying with privacy and security.

PHIRI methodology and tools have been used successfully to respond four research questions with different levels of analytical complexity and computational requirements.

PROVED VALUE OF PHIRI FEDERATED INFRASTRUCTURE

- 1 Successful deployment of four research projects involving 11 data hubs (data providing institutions) and a research network.
- 2 The PHIRI App has been visited 2,484 times, and downloaded for reuse 265 times
- 3 Other projects with heavier methodological, analytical and computational requirements are using PHIRI approach – see in some use cases of By-COVID or the EHDS2 pilot project

References

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